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Trust, Formal and Informal Market Institutions: Embeddedness

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Executive summary

This policy note examines the role of trust and institutions in enabling and constraining entrepreneurial behaviour. We explore the relationship between formal institutions and informal institutions and show how entrepreneurs often rely on informal institutional mechanisms in contexts where formal institutions are perceived as weak or dysfunctional. Using the concept of embeddedness, we argue that entrepreneurial activity is rooted in social relationships, networks and institutional contexts rather than operating in isolation. These networks shape access to information, resources and credibility particularly in uncertain environments. Our findings suggest that strong and reliable formal institutions support entrepreneurial growth and reduce transactional uncertainty. However, where confidence in formal institutions is limited, entrepreneurs rely more heavily on embedded social ties and informal institutional arrangements to overcome market challenges. In this sense, embedded networks and informal institutions become important mechanisms for sustaining entrepreneurial activity where formal institutional support is inadequate.

Overview

To begin, there is a bi-directional relationship between institutions and entrepreneurship. Institutions, understood here as the formal and informal rules, that structure social and economic interaction (North, 1990), can both enable and constrain entrepreneurial behaviour. On the one hand, institutions can reinforce forms of social interaction that produce productive

outcomes between actors (Platteau, 1994a, 1994b; Acemoglu and Robinson, 2012; Fafchamps, 2001; Moellering, 2006; Omeihe, 2023). On the other hand, institutions can foster rent-seeking behaviour and deviant or non-compliant entrepreneurial activity (North, 1990; Hodgson, 2006; Smallbone and Welter, 2012; Greif and Tabellini, 2010, 2012; Amoako and Lyon, 2014). Such emphasis is consistent with Baumol's (1990) notion of unproductive and destructive entrepreneurship. The logic of the argument is that informal institutions exist because they often compensate for the deficiencies of weak or ineffective formal institutional arrangements.

It is also particularly desirable in the present context that, among scholars who take seriously the embedded and social nature of entrepreneurship (for example, Lyon, 2005; Amoako, 2019; Omeihe and Omeihe, 2021; 2022), the analysis of institutions across Africa has often been characterised by conditions of incomplete markets and imperfect information. It is precisely at this point, however, that policymakers' interest in institutions faces the greatest difficulty with regard to empirical evidence. In the first place, there is a shortage of evidence, especially from an embeddedness perspective in challenging environments, about how entrepreneurial activity is shaped not only by formal rules and regulations but also by the social relationships and networks within which economic actors operate. This is the embeddedness view of Granovetter (1985).

These remarks, though necessary within the context of this policy discussion, are not intended to suggest a neglect of the formal dimensions of institutions. On the contrary, there is room to argue that where state-supported formal institutions are weak or ineffective, informal institutions and trust-based relationships assume increasingly important roles. Trust, in this paper, is understood as the expectation of reliability (Welter, 2012; Ariño and De la Torre, 1998), credibility and confidence (Gulati, 1995; Cummings and Bromiley, 1996) in social and economic exchange (Moellering, 2006; Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Zaheer et al., 1998).

Second, there is considerable evidence that, in many emerging market economies, weak enforcement and ineffective sanctioning mechanisms create uncertainty for SMEs. We can learn a great deal from pioneering work undertaken by scholars (see Puffer et al., 2010; Welter and Smallbone, 2011), which suggests that such weaknesses encourage non-compliant behaviour and arbitrary discretion among public officials. In such contexts, entrepreneurs often rely on embedded social networks and informal institutional arrangements to reduce uncertainty and build credibility.

While previous studies have examined the role of trade associations in relation to SMEs and the socio-economic challenges of developing environments (see Smith and Luttrell, 1994; Porter et al., 2007; Amoako, 2019; Omeihe and Omeihe, 2023), many important issues remain insufficiently addressed. Existing research has often overlooked the African context and has limited deeper understanding of the institutional realities shaping entrepreneurial behaviour. It is hoped that the findings presented here will provide a more accurate appreciation of why greater attention is needed to understand how trust, embedded social relationships and indigenous institutional arrangements support SMEs where formal institutional support is limited (see Algan and Cahuc, 2010; Amoako and Lyon, 2014; Omeihe et al., 2020).

The foregoing will be used in this policy paper as a point of departure for what is hoped will be a more contextual appraisal of the nature of institutions. And one which takes into account how trust functions as a critical mechanism for reducing uncertainty and supporting entrepreneurial interaction. The analysis presented in this paper is divided into three parts covering the following headings: discussion of the findings; policy and practical recommendations; and conclusions about the importance of strengthening formal institutional capacity.

Discussion of Key Findings

We now discuss the interpretation of our findings. Here, we present detailed qualitative evidence originating from two complementary but sophisticated sources. Our first source was derived from a set of interviews and intensive dialogues with 52 African entrepreneurs. This was further reinforced with observations, documentary evidence and case studies as multiple sources of evidence (Yin, 2014; Omeihe and Harrison, 2024). This approach allowed for an empirical inquiry into the often-unclear boundaries between context and the phenomenon being studied. To sum up, several of our findings suggest the following insights.

First, while previous studies have explored the relationship between entrepreneurship and institutions (Kalantaridis and Fletcher, 2012; Welter, 2011; Welter and Baker, 2021), this policy paper goes further by examining how trust, embedded social relationships and informal institutions continue to shape entrepreneurial activity in contexts where formal institutions are ineffective. Our findings show that entrepreneurs often rely on alternative institutional mechanisms, including trade associations, religion, kinship structures and personalised trust relationships, to sustain economic action. In doing so, it is necessary to correct the widespread impression outside policy circles that informal institutions are inherently inferior or less effective than formal institutions. Such views often derive from the assumption that institutions operate uniformly across contexts. Instead, the paper draws attention to the importance of understanding how entrepreneurial exchange is shaped not only by formal rules and regulations but also by the social and institutional networks within which economic actors operate.

Secondly, while formal institutions remain important for economic development, our findings reveal that many entrepreneurs continue to face uncertainty due to weak enforcement mechanisms and ineffective institutional support. There is therefore good reason to suggest that entrepreneurs often depend on embedded social networks and trust-based relationships to reduce uncertainty and identify new opportunities. However, it would be wrong to ignore that many participants highlighted the importance of reputation, reciprocity and personal credibility in shaping entrepreneurial relationships, particularly in contexts where formal contractual arrangements are not widely trusted or enforced.

Thirdly, we found strong evidence supporting the role of trade associations, religious institutions and community networks in supporting entrepreneurial activity. While it is impossible here to enter into a general discussion of all the issues involved, it is important to point out that this theme emerged consistently throughout the study. These institutional networks often provided practical support by facilitating access to information, referrals and trusted business

relationships. At present, and for current purposes, it can be said that our findings reinforce previous research suggesting that entrepreneurial activity is deeply embedded within social and institutional networks rather than operating independently of them (Granovetter, 1985; Nee and Ingram, 1998; Li, 2006; Amoako, 2019; Omeihe, 2023).

Lastly, there is one final aspect which needs to be stressed. While this paper highlights the important role that trust and informal institutions can play in supporting entrepreneurial exchange, the findings also reveal that some institutional arrangements can operate as constraints. In particular, certain religious and cultural expectations were found to limit opportunities for women entrepreneurs and shape patterns of exclusion within entrepreneurial activity. These findings point to the need for more balanced policy approaches that strengthen formal institutional capacity, while recognising the continuing influence of embedded social relationships and indigenous institutions in shaping entrepreneurial development.

Main Takeaways for Key Stakeholders

- **Entrepreneurship is shaped by both formal and informal institutions:** Entrepreneurial activity is influenced not only by laws and regulations, but also by trust-based relationships, kinship ties and informal networks. This particularly affects SMEs and informal traders, especially in developing economies where SMEs account for over 90% of businesses globally (see IFC Report, 2024)
- **Trust becomes economically important where formal institutions are weak:** Where legal enforcement is weak, entrepreneurs often rely more on reputation, reciprocity and personalised trust than formal contracts. This directly affects SME owners, suppliers and lenders who depend on relational trust to reduce uncertainty and sustain exchange.
- **Embedded networks provide access to opportunities and support:** Trade associations, religious communities and social networks often help entrepreneurs gain access to information, finance, referrals and business opportunities. This is especially important for start-ups, migrant entrepreneurs and family businesses operating with limited institutional support.
- **Informal institutions act as alternative governance systems: Community-based** institutions and trade associations frequently support business continuity by enforcing informal rules, resolving disputes and promoting trust where state systems are ineffective. This strongly affects local business communities and informal market actors.
- **Informal institutions can both support and constrain entrepreneurship:** While informal institutions may provide protection and support, they can also reinforce exclusionary cultural norms that restrict opportunities, particularly for women entrepreneurs and marginalised groups. Gender gaps in access to finance and entrepreneurial participation remain significant across many developing economies.
- **Policy responses must reflect institutional realities:** Effective policy requires stronger formal institutions alongside greater recognition of embedded social relationships and informal governance systems. This is particularly important for policymakers,

development agencies and financial institutions seeking to promote sustainable and inclusive entrepreneurial growth.

Policy and Practice Recommendations

This strategy adopted in this policy paper has been to state the argument at the outset that institutions matter, and then to develop that informal institutions also have a role to play. We will briefly capture the main points of interpretation for policy makers.

At an economic level, the central theme is that the informal sector provides opportunities for employment and sustainable growth. Policymakers should therefore seek to create conducive environments that facilitate entrepreneurship. The present work has noted the inaccuracies of a generalised view of institutions and shows that future policy should acknowledge that entrepreneurs play an important role in African development and must therefore be properly supported. There are various African perspectives that need to be considered in order to capture a satisfactory account of institutions and their embeddedness within entrepreneurial action.

Accordingly, the interpretation put forward here challenges government interference in the informal sector through restrictive policies, a point that will be familiar to economists specialising in emerging markets. The analysis presented here principally argues that policy decisions should instead seek to enhance the development of the sector. Rather than adopting the questionable view of abolishing informal sectors, which greatly exaggerates the separation between formal and informal economic activity, policymakers should recognise the complementary relationship that exists between them. This conclusion is important and aligns with recent research on African institutions (see Omeihe, 2026)

At the same time, it is important to note that the entrepreneurs interviewed for the original study (see Omeihe, 2019; Omeihe and Omeihe, 2024), expressed negative concerns about government institutions. This demands the mobilisation and implementation of policies that address inefficiencies across formal institutions. In this regard, it is quite clear that lessons drawn from the institutional success stories of countries such as Singapore, Japan and South Korea may contribute towards strengthening institutional reforms across the continent.

The paper also provides more direct policy implications. Two notable features are worth highlighting for purposes of comparison. First, following the methodology and framework adopted, the role of embedded network ties is important for 'bridging the psychic distance' between domestic and international markets. These ties, which are built on trust, involve collaborations across socio-cultural networks and markets. It is therefore important to understand how entrepreneurs operate in contexts characterised by institutional deficiencies, rather than assuming that institutional conditions can simply be transplanted across contexts.

Second, it would appear that a way forward for policymakers is the development of institutions in ways that are beneficial both to entrepreneurs and government. In this way, entrepreneurs would be more likely to rely on efficient government institutions to support their entrepreneurial activities. Over time, such developments could strengthen the growth and competitiveness of

African entrepreneurship. Furthermore, it is wrong to assume that entrepreneurs operating within the informal sector are primarily engaged in contraband trade or tax avoidance. This is not necessarily the case.

From the assertions made by participants, poverty and limited economic opportunities remain major drivers of informal entrepreneurial activity. While many governmental reforms have focused primarily on investors and large corporations, further policy approaches need to give greater consideration to entrepreneurs operating within challenging institutional environments, as many continue to remain disconnected from broader economic progress. Through this, government actions may contribute more effectively to economic growth and increased GDP.

Policy Recommendations

- **Governments must build institutions that entrepreneurs can trust:** Where contract enforcement is weak and regulations are inconsistently applied, entrepreneurs shift away from long-term investment towards short-term survival strategies. More reliable legal systems and predictable regulation would reduce uncertainty and support productive exchange between SMEs, investors and suppliers.
- **Entrepreneurial activity should be understood as socially embedded rather than purely market-driven:** Entrepreneurs operate not only through formal rules, but through networks of trust, kinship ties, trade associations and community relationships that shape access to information, finance and market opportunities in practice.
- **States should work with trade associations and local business networks rather than treating them as peripheral actors:** In many developing economies, these organisations already provide coordination, dispute resolution and informal governance where formal institutions remain weak or ineffective.
- **Financial institutions should recognise relational trust as an economic resource:** Many SMEs and informal entrepreneurs remain excluded from formal finance because lending systems rely heavily on collateral and formal records while ignoring social reputation, embedded credibility and long-standing business relationships.
- **Reducing arbitrary state behaviour is central to entrepreneurial development:** Corruption, inconsistent enforcement and bureaucratic discretion weaken business confidence and increase the costs of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs respond to incentives, and weak institutions often encourage informality and non-compliant behaviour.
- **Policymakers should recognise that formal and informal institutions often operate together rather than separately:** Entrepreneurs frequently navigate both simultaneously, by relying on formal regulation where possible and embedded social relationships where formal institutions fail to provide certainty or support.
- **Governments should avoid punitive approaches towards the informal sector:** Many entrepreneurs operate informally not out of preference, but because poverty,

unemployment and limited formal opportunities leave few alternatives. Restrictive regulation may therefore weaken economic resilience rather than strengthen development.

- ***Institutional reform should focus on rebuilding trust in public systems:*** Where entrepreneurs do not trust courts, regulators or state institutions, they substitute formal exchange with personalised trust arrangements and informal systems of coordination.

Limitations

As with any study, ours has its own limitations, particularly with respect to the number of respondents. A broader empirical base would undoubtedly strengthen the scope for future inquiry. Nevertheless, the findings presented here point to issues that are both timely and institutionally significant. Future research could usefully extend this analysis through comparative examination across different African contexts, sectors and institutional environments to deepen our understanding of how trust, embeddedness and institutional structures shape entrepreneurial behaviour.

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